

A Potentiometric Study of the Reduction by Ferrous Ions of Potassium Iodate in Phosphoric, Sulphuric and Hydrochloric Acid Solutions

N. B. MAZUMDAR, K. CHATTERJEE and S. N. DAS*

Physical Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna 800005

Manuscript received 5 September 1974; accepted 21 February 1975

Potassium iodate can be accurately titrated potentiometrically with ferrous ion in phosphoric and sulphuric acid solutions over a wide range (8N to 30N) of sufficiently high concentration, the reduction proceeding directly to iodine.

Titration is also possible in hydrochloric acid solutions, but the mechanism of the reduction process is no longer given by the equation

Two inflexions in the titration curve correspond to the initial reduction of iodic acid almost quantitatively to ICl_3 , and its subsequent reduction to ICl . The second inflexion at about 3.5 moles however, is not sharp and appears before the required amount of 4 moles of titrant has been added.

UNDER ordinary conditions reduction of iodic acid by ferrous ion is a slow process and Vulterin¹ used osmium sulphate as a catalyst in the potentiometric titration of potassium iodate by ferrous ammonium sulphate in phosphoric acid solutions. In the present work the possibility of carrying out accurate titrations, in different acid media without using a catalyst, was explored. Accordingly, titrations were carried out in phosphoric, sulphuric and hydrochloric acid solutions over a wide range of concentration.

Experimental

A bright platinum foil electrode coupled with a suitable reference electrode ($\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{Hg}$, sat. KCl in HCl titrations and $\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Hg}$, 0.5M H_2SO_4 in H_2SO_4 and H_3PO_4 titrations) was used in the titration cell containing 150 ml of 0.001M KIO_3 in different acid solutions. Chemicals used were of analytical grade. The titrations were all done in room temperature (ca. 35°) in an atmosphere of nitrogen. A potentiometer reading up to ± 0.5 mV was used. In most cases steady potential values were obtained after thorough stirring (by a magnetic stirrer) for 15 min on each addition of the titrant. The titrant solution, 0.1M $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 2M H_2SO_4 , was stored in nitrogen atmosphere and was periodically standardised² against standard $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.

Results

(i) *Titration in phosphoric and sulphuric acid solutions*: Fig. 1 contains typical curves of the titration in the presence of phosphoric acid of following concentrations: (A) 8N, (B) 12N, (C) 16N,

(D) 20N, (E) 24N, (F) 28N and (G) 32N. On addition of the first few drops of Fe^{2+} solution, the reaction mixture turned reddish brown and changed to dark red at the inflexion points and ultimately iodine was precipitated. At all the concentrations the inflexions occurred with the addition of exactly 5 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole KIO_3 .

Fig. 2 refers to similar titrations in the presence of sulphuric acid of following concentrations: (A) 6N, (B) 10N, (C) 14N, (D) 18N, (E) 22N, (F) 26N and (G) 30N. The solutions were red on the addition of titrant and the colour darkened as the titration proceeded. Again, as in the case of phosphoric acid solutions, inflexions occurred with the addition of exactly 5 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole of IO_3^- .

In lower acid concentrations (< 8N H_3PO_4 and < 6N H_2SO_4) the titrations could not be successfully carried out as the reaction was slow and potentials were not steady.

(ii) *Titrations in hydrochloric acid solutions*: The relevant titration curves appear in Fig. 3 for titrations in hydrochloric acid solutions of following concentrations: (A) 3N, (B) 4N, (C) 5N, (D) 6N, (E) 7N, (F) 8N and (G) 9N. The initial pale yellow colour which the titrate developed on the first addition of the titrant, changed to orange red as the titration progressed. Two inflexions appeared in the curves (A) to (D): the first well defined and sharp inflexion requiring 2 moles Fe^{2+} and the second inflexion, a small break in the curve at about 3.5 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole of IO_3^- . The second inflexion tends to disappear with hydrochloric acid concentration increasing beyond 7N.

* For correspondence.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Discussion

In phosphoric and in sulphuric acid solutions, provided the acid concentrations are sufficiently high (between 8N to 30N) a mole of KIO_3^- requires 5 moles Fe^{2+} for reduction. This corresponds with :

the reduction of IO_3^- proceeding directly to iodine. A reference to oxidation potential values given in Table 1 (table constructed mainly from Latimer³ and from Swift⁴) reveals that the redox reaction (1)

TABLE 1—STANDARD AND FORMAL ELECTRODE POTENTIALS AT 25°

Half reaction	E° , volts, vs N.H.E.	E° , volts, vs. N.H.E.
$\text{Fe}^{3+} + e = \text{Fe}^{2+}$	0.77	0.70(1M HCl) 0.66(4M HCl) 0.68(1M H_2SO_4) 0.66(8M, H_2SO_4) 0.61(1M H_2SO_4 + 0.5M H_3PO_4)
$\text{IO}_3^- + 3\text{Cl}^- + 6\text{H}^+ + 2e = \text{ICl}_3 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.07	—
$\text{IO}_3^- + \text{Cl}^- + 6\text{H}^+ + 4e = \text{ICl} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.20	—
$\text{IO}_3^- + 6\text{H}^+ + 5e = \frac{1}{2}\text{I}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.20	—
$\text{IO}_3^- + 2\text{Cl}^- + 6\text{H}^+ + 4e = \text{ICl}_2^- + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.23	—
$\text{ICl}_3 + 3e = \frac{1}{2}\text{I}_2 + 3\text{Cl}^-$	1.28	—
$\text{ICl}_3 + 2e = \text{ICl} + 2\text{Cl}^-$	1.31	—

is associated with an appreciable driving potential. In lower acid concentrations the reaction was found to be too slow to be of practical importance. This slowness might be attributed to the existence of a large energy barrier in the path of the reaction in low acid concentrations. It may be noted that in higher acid concentrations, the formal potentials (E°) of the $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ couple are substantially less than the corresponding standard electrode potential (E°) as shown in Table 1; this would render Fe^{2+} an even more powerful reductant, a point also noted by Rao and Sagi⁵. Formal potentials of the $\text{IO}_3^-/\frac{1}{2}\text{I}_2$ couple might similarly render it a more powerful oxidant in concentrated acid solutions. Both these factors would account for a larger driving potential for the above reaction.

In hydrochloric acid solutions the situation with regard to the reduction of IO_3^- seems to be basically changed. Requirement of 2 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole of IO_3^- at the first inflexion, which is sharp and well defined at moderately high concentrations of the acid, indicate that in the first step IO_3^- may be completely reduced to ICl_3 :

The second inflexion, a small break, requires about 3.5 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole of IO_3^- . If ICl_3 is reduced to ICl_2^- in the next step, a further 2 moles of Fe^{2+} would be consumed :

which would thus amount to the net reaction :

requiring a total of 4 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole of IO_3^- , the reduction process ultimately yielding iodine monochloride. This scheme is in accord with the observation, first made by Andrews⁶, that IO_3^- in strong HCl solutions is ultimately reduced to ICl (or ICl_2^- , which is a stable complex ion formed from ICl) which has since become the basis of standard analytical procedure⁷. Oxidation potential values (listed above) also predict that IO_3^- , in presence of Cl^- , would preferentially be reduced to iodine monochloride rather than to iodine. Actual inflexions are at about 3.5 moles of Fe^{2+} , — 0.5 moles less than what is required by equation (4). Proximity of oxidation potential values of ICl_3/ICl and $\text{ICl}_3/\frac{1}{2}\text{I}_2$ couples indicate that some ICl_3 might be reduced to I_2 at this stage and no distinct inflexion would occur marking the formation of the latter.

Iodine trichloride has been isolated as a solid^{8,9} and Nies and Yost¹⁰ have measured its thermodynamic properties. However, consideration of concerned oxidation potential data fails to explain why, during reduction of IO_3^- in presence of HCl, ICl_3 should first be formed in preference to ICl_2^- , (or even I_2), for, the value of E° for the $\text{IO}_3^-/\text{ICl}_3$ couple appears to be lower than those of $\text{IO}_3^-/\text{ICl}_2^-$ and $\text{IO}_3^-/\frac{1}{2}\text{I}_2$ couple. We should however show particular reluctance to accept the listed E° value for the $\text{IO}_3^-/\text{ICl}_3$ couple as representing the true state of affairs under experimental conditions—perhaps the corresponding formal potential values (possibly due to ICl_3 forming complex ions with Cl^-) are appreciably larger. The measurement of formal potentials involving intermediate oxidation states of iodine merits further investigation and this matter is receiving our attention.

References

1. J. VULTERIN, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1966, **31**, 2501.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, 1962, p. 309.
3. W. M. LATIMER, "Oxidation Potentials", Prentice-Hall, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1956.
4. E. H. SWIFT, "Introductory Quantitative Analysis", Prentice-Hall, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1950.
5. G. G. RAO and S. R. SAGI, *Talanta*, 1962, **9**, 715.
6. L. W. ANDREWS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **25**, 756.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, 1962, p. 374.
8. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1972, p. 584.
9. P. J. DURRANT and B. DURRANT, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1962, p. 902.
10. N. P. NIES and D. M. YOST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 306.